

JASMIN

The UK's data analysis facility for environmental science

What is JASMIN?

- A bespoke high-throughput computing (HTC) environmental science facility, fulfilling requirements for high-performance data analysis in the environmental science community
- Over 2000 users conducting collaborative research on climate change, oceanography, air pollution, earthquake deformation...
- Access to curated archives of Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA), a key part of NERC's environmental data service
- Users can develop code interactively, then scale up onto a Slurm-based CPU & GPU cluster, or "roll their own" compute in the JASMIN Community Cloud

Who runs JASMIN?

- A cross-department and cross-research council collaboration between environmental data science experts in CEDA and technical skills of Scientific Computing Department
- CEDA team develop and operate user services, SCD team implement and operate hardware (10,000s of CPU cores, PBs of storage and tape)
- Together provisioning services for the wider NERC community, including NCAS, Met Office, plus NERC-related researchers in universities and institutions in the UK and abroad
- Example projects include COMET (Centre for Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes, Volcanoes, and Tectonics) and PRIMAVERA who develop high-resolution global climate models

Science and Technology Facilities Council
Natural Environment Research Council

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<https://jasmin.ac.uk>